

PHARMACEUTICAL AND ANALYTICAL EVALUATION OF KRITRIMA HARATALA W.S.R TO RASA TARANGINI

Dr. Sumant Dayanand Gunaga*¹, Dr. Ravi R. Chavan MD (ayu)², Dr. Lalitha MD (ayu)³

*¹Final Year PG Scholar, Department of Post Graduate Studies in Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana.

²Professor & HOD, Department of Post Graduate Studies in Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana.

³Assistant Professor, Department of Post Graduate Studies in Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana.

*^{1,2,3}Taranath Govt. Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Ballari. Karnataka, India.

Article Received on 07 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 27 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17801512>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Sumant Dayanand Gunaga

Final Year PG Scholar, Department of Post Graduate Studies in Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Taranath Govt. Ayurvedic Medical College and Hospital, Ballari. Karnataka, India.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Sumant Dayanand Gunaga*¹, Dr. Ravi R. Chavan MD (ayu)², Dr. Lalitha MD (ayu)³. (2025). Pharmaceutical and analytical evaluation of kritrima haratala w.s.r to rasa tarangini. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 1063–1079.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Rasashastra is a specialized branch of Ayurveda that deals with the transformation and processing of metals, minerals, and other natural substances for therapeutic and alchemical purposes. Among these, Haratala (Orpiment) is an important mineral drug widely mentioned in classical texts for its medicinal value. It is classically employed in the treatment of Śleşmaroga, Raktapitta, Vatarakta, and Kuṣṭha. The present study focuses on the artificial preparation (Kṛtrima Nirmaṇa) of Haratala using Shuddha Gauripaṣhaṇa^[2] and Shuddha Gandhaka^[3] by using Damaru Yantra^[4], as described in Rasatarangini. The process was carried out under controlled conditions to replicate the traditional synthesis. The prepared Kṛtrima Haratala^[1] was subjected to various analytical evaluations to determine its crystalline structure, particle size, elemental composition, and functional groups. The analytical results confirmed the formation of Kṛtrima Haratala with

properties comparable to natural orpiment. This study validates the traditional method of Rasashastra through modern analytical techniques, emphasizing its reproducibility, standardization, and potential for safe therapeutic application.

KEYWORDS: Kritrima Haratala; Gauripashana; Gandhaka; Rasa Tarangini; Artificial preparation of orpiment.

INTRODUCTION

Haratala is a well-known mineral used extensively in *Rasa Shastra*, the branch of Ayurveda dealing with alchemical and herbo-mineral preparations. Traditionally, *Haratala* is utilized after undergoing a series of purification and incineration processes to ensure its safety and therapeutic efficacy. However, the natural availability of *Haratala* is becoming limited, and concerns about consistency in quality have led to a growing interest in the artificial synthesis of *Haratala* using purified ingredients.

In this context, the use of *Shuddha Gandhaka* and *Shuddha Gauripashana* offers a reproducible and potentially safer alternative for the preparation of *Haratala* in a controlled laboratory environment. The artificial method also allows for better standardization and minimization of toxicological risks when appropriate protocols are followed.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

AIM

PHARMACEUTICO-ANALYTICAL STUDY OF KRITRIMA HARATALA.

OBJECTIVES

To purify *Gandhaka* and *Gauripashana* following the *Śodhana* using classical *Śodhana* techniques.

To carry out the artificial preparation of *Haratala* using the *Damaru Yantra* method outlined in *Rasatarangini*.

To analyze the prepared *Haratala* using modern analytical techniques.

METHODOLOGY

Raw drugs exhibiting *Grahya Lakṣaṇas*^[5,6] (acceptable characteristics) as described in classical *Rasasastra* texts were identified and procured from the local market.

Gandhaka Shodhana

- A clean earthen pot was taken and its inner surface was smeared with 10 ml of *Go-ghrita*⁷. Subsequently, 1.5 litres of fresh cow's milk^[8] was poured into it.

- The mouth of the pot was covered with a layer of kora cloth and securely tied with a thread.
- Over this cloth, a uniform layer of *Gandhaka* was spread and the setup was covered with a Loha Sharava.
- The Loha Sharava was then covered with 11 cow-dung cakes weighing approximately 1.05 kg, and the fire was ignited using camphor.
- After *Swanga Sheeta*, the pot was taken out of the pit and the cloth covering its mouth was removed.
- The granules of *Shodhita Gandhaka* settled at the bottom were collected, thoroughly washed with hot water, and dried in shade.

Gauripashana Shodhana

- Raw *Gauripashana* was first broken into small pieces to facilitate better exposure to the purification medium.
- The pieces were then placed inside fresh *Karavellaka Phala*^[9] (*bitter gourd*), which was slit open and used as a natural enclosure.
- This combination was then securely wrapped using a thread and enclosed in a clean Kora cloth to form a *Pottali*.
- The *Pottali* was subjected to *Swedana* in a *Dola Yantra* using *Karavellaka Swarasa* as the medium, and the process was carried out continuously for 3 hours.

Kritrima Haratala Nirmana

- 49 grams of *Shuddha Gauripashana* and 24gms *Shuddha Gandhaka* were weighed and triturated together in a clean mortar for a duration of two hours to obtain a homogeneous mixture.
- The resulting blend was then evenly spread in the lower pot of a Damaru Yantra, a traditional Ayurvedic apparatus used for sublimation processes.
- To ensure an airtight seal, the joints of the apparatus were closed using a paste made from Multani Mitti and Kora cloth, applied uniformly in seven successive layers.
- Following this, the sealed apparatus was dried and subjected to gradual heat for three hours.
- *Toyadhara* a constant water stream above the upper chamber was maintained throughout the heating process to regulate the condensation and sublimation environment.

- Upon completion of the heating period, the apparatus was allowed to self-cool at room temperature.
- Once completely cooled, the Damaru Yantra was carefully dismantled.
- A yellow-colored sublimated material, resembling classical *Haratala*, was found deposited in the upper chamber. This material was gently scraped, collected, and preserved for further analysis.

RESULTS

Pharmaceutico-Analytical study results are described under 2 headings.

1. Pharmaceutical results

2. Analytical results

1. Pharmaceutical Results

Showing results from Gandhaka Shodhana.

Quantity of milk Used	No. of Vanopalas used	Initial Wt of Crude <i>Gandhaka</i>	Final Wt of Sh. <i>Gandhaka</i>	Total Loss	Yield
1.5 litres	11	250 gms	225gms	25gms	90%

2. Showing results from Gauripashana Shodhana.

Quantity of Karavellaka swarasa Used	Initial weight of Crude Gauripashana	Final weight of Shuddha Gauripashana	Total Loss	Yield
4L	100gms	95gms	5gms	95%

3. Showing results from Kritrima Haratala.

Weight of Shuddha Gauripashana	Weight of Shuddha Gandhaka	Duration of Heat	Weight of Kritrima Haratala	Total Loss	Yield
49gms	24gms	3 hours	40gms	33gms	54.79%

2. Analytical Results

Showing Results of Organoleptic characters of Kritrima Haratala

Physical Tests	Kritrima Haratala
Colour	Yellow
Odour	Arsenic
Taste	Astringent
Touch	Fine

Showing XRD results Kritrima Haratala

Sample	Chemical Formula	Crystalline Structure
Kritrima Haratala	As ₂ S ₃	Monoclinic

Showing SEM EDS result of Kritrima Haratala

Element	Weight %	Atomic %
C	22.71	50.72
O	21.55	30.14
S	9.59	6.69
As	41.65	12.44

Showing Particle Size of Kritrima Haratala

Sample	Mean Diameter
Kritrima Haratala	1144.8nm

Showing FTIR Peaks of Kritrima Haratala

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group / Bond	Interpretation
2981.21	C–H stretch (aliphatic)	Indicates aliphatic hydrocarbons.
1979.83	Overtone/combination band	Likely an overtone or metal–ligand feature.
1259.32	C–O / C–N stretch or S=O vibration	Suggests oxygen/nitrogen groups or lattice vibrations.
1039.36	C–O / C–N stretch or S–O vibration	Indicates oxygen-containing groups or inorganic vibrations.
786.73	C–H out-of-plane bending / lattice mode	Represents aromatic substitution or inorganic lattice mode.

Pictures***Gandhaka Shodhana******Powdered Gandhaka***

Ghrita Lipta Pot

Ksheera poured in pot

Gandhaka Placed in Kurma Puta

Ignition

Shuddha Gandhaka

Gauripashana Shodhana

Raw Gauripashana

Placed in Karavellaka Phala

Tied through thread

Addition of Karavellaka Swarasa

After Shodhana

Shuddha Gauripashana

Shuddha Gandhaka

Homogenized mixture at the base Of lower pot

Damaru Yantra

Lower Pot

Haratala Sublimated at the Upper Pot.

XRD Graph of Kritrima Haratala.

SEM EDS of Kritrima Haratala.

FTIR of Kritrima Haratala.

Particle Size of Kritrima Haratala.

DISCUSSION

Discussion on Gandhaka Shodhana

Go-Ghrita^[7] acts as a *Yogavahi* and detoxifier facilitates the extraction of impurities from Gandhaka by softening and lubricating its surface. Cow's Milk^[8] possesses both *Snigdha* and *Sheeta* properties, helping to neutralize the *Teekshna* nature of raw Gandhaka. The earthen pot provides a neutral, inert vessel that doesn't react with the ingredients.

Use of Loha Sharava offers heat resistance and structural stability during heating. Use of cow dung cakes provides a controlled, uniform heating pattern promoting gentle purification. The heating causes the Gandhaka to melt and vaporize, allowing volatile and non-volatile impurities to be removed, purified Gandhaka separates out in granule form, leaving behind non-sublimable impurities.

Contact with milk vapors and ghee during heating aids detoxification, reduces pungency, and introduces medicinal properties. Change in odor: Raw Gandhaka has a strong, unpleasant odor which is significantly reduced post-purification.

Change in color and texture: From a darker, more brittle or greasy appearance to a brighter yellow and softer crystalline granule form.

Swanga Sheetā ensures complete settling and safety in handling the setup post-heating. Washing with hot water: Essential to remove residual milk fats, ghee, and any leftover impurities.

Drying in shade: Protects the integrity of the purified Gandhaka from direct sunlight, which might affect its potency or structure.

Discussion on Gauripashana Shodhana

Initially, the *Gauripashana* was broken down into smaller fragments to increase surface area and ensure maximum interaction with the purification medium.

This mechanical size reduction is crucial for facilitating deeper penetration of the *Swarasa* during *Swedana*, thereby ensuring better removal of impurities and toxic elements.

Bitter gourd is traditionally known for its detoxifying properties and is rich in bioactive compounds such as momordicin, charantin, and alkaloids that possess antimicrobial and

antioxidant properties. Its juice likely plays a synergistic role in binding or neutralizing toxic constituents in *Gauripashaṇa*, contributing to chemical purification.

Wrapping the mineral pieces inside *Karavellaka* and securing it with *Kora* cloth into a *Pottali* provides a controlled environment for uniform heating and ensures no direct contamination or loss of material during the *Swedana* process.

The Dola Yantra setup allows continuous exposure to the medium in a suspended manner, ensuring optimal interaction between the *Shodhaniya Dravya* and *Shodhana Dravya*.

The *Swedana* was conducted using *Karavellaka Swarasa* for 3 hours, which is traditionally prescribed as sufficient duration for effective purification.

The process enables the mineral to undergo thermal and chemical transformation while retaining its therapeutic integrity.

The acidic and enzymatic nature of the bitter gourd juice may also assist in leaching out water-soluble toxic substances or neutralizing potentially harmful components.

Discussion on Kritrima Haratala Nirmana

The present procedure outlines a classical approach for the artificial preparation of *Haratala* through the controlled sublimation of *Shuddha Gauripashaṇa* and *Shuddha Gandhaka* following the principles of Rasa Shastra.

The method demonstrates a precise application of traditional pharmaceutics using the *Damaru Yantra*, which is specifically designed for sublimation-based transformations of mineral substances.

In this method, the initial step of trituration for two hours ensured intimate mixing and uniform distribution of *Gauripashaṇa* and *Gandhaka*. The mechanical blending facilitates molecular interaction and homogenizes the reactive components, which is essential for effective sublimation and transformation during the heating process.

The use of the *Damaru Yantra*, a closed sublimation chamber, plays a vital role in controlling the thermal environment, preventing the escape of volatile arsenic compounds, and directing the sublimated matter towards deposition in the upper chamber.

Sealing the apparatus with Multani Mitti and Kora cloth in seven layers is a traditional yet scientifically sound method to create an airtight seal, ensuring safety, pressure control, and containment of toxic fumes.

Multani Mitti acts as a thermal insulator and binding agent, while the layered cloth provides structural integrity during heating. The graduated heat application for three hours mimics the classical *Mandagni to Tivragni* pattern, promoting gradual sublimation without thermal shock. The regulated heating minimizes the risk of decomposition or uncontrolled volatilization of arsenic and sulfur compounds.

The implementation of Toyadhara a continuous water stream over the upper chamber—is particularly significant. It helps in maintaining a condensation-friendly thermal gradient, allowing efficient sublimation and subsequent deposition of the *Haratala* in crystalline form. This technique also prevents overheating of the upper chamber, which could otherwise disturb the crystallization or cause re-evaporation of the sublimated product.

After the cooling phase, dismantling the apparatus revealed a yellow sublimated material deposited on the inner surface of the upper chamber.

The color, texture, and deposition pattern of the product closely resembled classical descriptions of *Haratala*, indicating successful sublimation and transformation.

Discussion on Analytical Parameters

Discussion on XRD

The XRD analysis of the artificially prepared *Haratala* confirms the successful formation of crystalline arsenic trisulfide (As_2S_3), corresponding to monoclinic orpiment with $\text{P2}_1/\text{n}$ space group.

Sharp diffraction peaks observed at 2θ values around 15° , 23° , 28° , 33° , 36° , 45° , 50° , and 55° align well with standard reference data (JCPDS 42-1396), indicating high crystallinity and phase purity.

The absence of peaks related to unreacted As_2O_3 or elemental sulphur suggests a complete chemical transformation. The close match between measured and calculated patterns further confirms the identity of the product as *Haratala*.

These results validate the traditional sublimation method using the *Damaru Yantra* and demonstrate the potential of this process for producing pharmaceutically acceptable, standardized *Haratala*.

Discussion on SEM EDS

The SEM-EDS analysis of the artificially prepared *Haratala* indicates a deviation from pure orpiment (As_2S_3) composition, with low sulfur (9.59 wt%), moderate arsenic (41.65 wt%), and elevated oxygen levels.

Since As_2O_3 was used as the precursor, the high oxygen content likely results from incomplete sulfidation, leaving behind residual arsenic oxide or forming mixed oxide-sulfide phases.

The presence of carbon may be due to organic handling materials or mounting on carbon tape. These findings suggest the need for optimizing reaction conditions to ensure complete conversion to phase-pure *Haratala* (As_2S_3).

Discussion on Particle Size

The particle size analysis of artificial *Haratala* revealed an average diameter of 1144.8 nm (1.14 μm) placing it in the microparticle range.

This is acceptable at the current stage, as further incineration (*Marana*) and processing are expected to reduce the size further toward the nanoscale, as required in final Ayurvedic formulations.

The Polydispersity Index (PDI) of 0.389 indicates moderate polydispersity, suggesting a mixed particle population, which is typical before final processing.

The baseline index of 0.0 confirms the reliability of the measurement with no instrumental noise. The lognormal size distribution, skewed toward larger particles, reflects initial aggregation or non-uniform grinding commonly observed in pre-incinerated samples.

Overall, the sample is suitably refined for its current stage and shows potential for further transformation into a pharmaceutically acceptable form through traditional Ayurvedic methods.

Discussion on FTIR

FTIR analysis of the artificial Haratala sample revealed key absorptions indicating both inorganic and organic components.

The peak at 2981 cm^{-1} corresponds to C–H stretching, suggesting the presence of aliphatic organic residues, possibly from synthesis precursors or surface contaminants.

Absorptions at 1259 cm^{-1} and 1039 cm^{-1} may be attributed to C–O, S=O, or C–N functional groups, further indicating the presence of organic or oxidized surface species.

Crucially, the peak at 786 cm^{-1} is consistent with As–S lattice vibrations, confirming the formation of orpiment (As_2S_3). These results suggest that while the core crystalline structure is present, the sample may still carry residual organic or oxidative by-products.

This supports the conclusion that the material is in an intermediate state synthesized but not yet fully purified or processed for medicinal use.

Comparison Table: Artificial Haratala vs Standard Orpiment.

Metric	Artificial Haratala (Sample)	Standard Orpiment (Reference)	Interpretation
XRD – Crystallinity	Sharp peaks at 15° , 23° , 28° , 33° , 36° , 45° , 50° , 55° (2θ); phase matches JCPDS 42-1396	Matches standard As_2S_3 pattern (monoclinic orpiment)	Excellent phase purity and crystallinity confirmed; no residual As_2O_3 or S found.
XRD – Space Group	$P2_1/n$ (Monoclinic)	$P2_1/n$ (Monoclinic)	Confirms structural identity as orpiment.
SEM-EDS – Arsenic (As)	41.65 wt%	~60.91 wt% (for pure As_2S_3)	Lower As content suggests incomplete conversion or oxide contamination.
SEM-EDS – Sulfur (S)	9.59 wt%	~39.09 wt% (for pure As_2S_3)	Significantly lower; suggests incomplete sulfidation or loss of sulfur.
SEM-EDS – Oxygen (O)	Elevated (value not specified, inferred as high)	~0% (pure As_2S_3 contains no O)	Indicates residual As_2O_3 or mixed oxide-sulfide phases.
Particle Size – Avg.	1144.8 nm (1.14 μm)	Nanoscale preferred post-Marana (often <100 nm)	Micron-scale is acceptable for pre-Marana; size will

			reduce in incineration.
PDI (Polydispersity)	0.389	Ideal < 0.2 for uniform particles	Moderate polydispersity; acceptable at this stage, needs refinement.
FTIR – As–S Peak	Present at 786 cm ⁻¹	780–790 cm ⁻¹ typical for As–S bonds	Confirms orpiment structure is formed.
FTIR – C–H Stretch	Present at 2981 cm ⁻¹	Absent in pure inorganic sample	Indicates organic residues; possibly from handling or precursor contamination.

CONCLUSION

The study confirms the successful synthesis of *Kṛitrima Haratala* (As₂S₃) through the classical Damaru Yantra method using purified *Gauripaṣhaṇa* and *Gandhaka*. XRD analysis verified the formation of monoclinic crystalline orpiment with high phase purity. FTIR and SEM-EDS indicated the presence of residual organic and oxygen-containing compounds, suggesting incomplete sulfidation and the need for further purification. Particle size analysis showed an average size of 1.14 μm with moderate polydispersity, acceptable at this pre-incineration stage. Overall, the product represents a suitable intermediate for further Ayurvedic processing to achieve a pharmaceutically acceptable form for therapeutic use.

REFERENCES

1. Gautam DS. *Rasatarangini*. 11th Taranga: Taalakaadi Vijnaneeya, Verses 9–12. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, 2022; 225.
2. Gautam DS. *Rasatarangini*. 8th Taranga: Gandhaka Vijnaneeya, Verses 13–17. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, 2022; 162–163.
3. Mishra SN. *Rasa Ratna Samuccaya*. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 3rd Adhyaya, Sadharana Varga. Verse 2021; 128: 87.
4. Gautam DS. *Rasatarangini*. 4th Taranga: Yantra Vijnaneeya. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, 2022; 50–51.
5. Gautam DS. *Rasatarangini*. 8th Taranga: Gandhaka Vijnaneeya, Verse 4. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, 2022; 161.
6. Mishra SN. *Rasa Ratna Samuccaya*. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 3rd Adhyaya, Sadharana Varga. Verse 2021; 127: 87.

7. Vāgbhaṭa. *Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya*, Sūtrasthāna, Chapter 5, Dravyādi Vijnānīya Adhyāya. In: Paradakara HS, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy, 2018; 38.
8. Vāgbhaṭa. *Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya*, Sūtrasthāna, Chapter 5, Dravyādi Vijnānīya Adhyāya. In: Paradakara HS, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy, 2018; 38.
9. Mishra B, editor. *Bhāvaprakāśa Nighaṇṭu* of Bhāvamiśra. Harītakyaḍi Varga. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2020; 412.